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The Effects of E- Media and Social Networking Site Usage on the Mental Health and Wellbeing of Adolescents : A Review Study

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ABSTRACT

To systematically review empirical studies conducted over the past 10 years on this topic to reach a consensus on the impact of e-media and social networking use on adolescents. To identify any variables or predispositions that may moderate these effects. A systematic review of research published between 2008 and 2018 obtained from a database search. Results were analyzed using a narrative synthesis approach and examined within the following frameworks: harmful exposure, peer support, and addiction. The database search found 15 relevant studies. E-media and social networking sites have been reported to be beneficial in providing mutual support, a sense of acceptance among peers, as well as a way to maintain social connections. Harmful effects included potential addiction, exposure to harmful experiences, and increased risk of psychological problems. Variables that increased the risk of negative effects were younger age, engaging with sites for more than 2-3 hours per day, and starting use at a younger age.

Keywords : E-media, Social Networking sites, Mental Health, Adolescents

INTRODUCTION

Young adults growing up in the 21st century spend much of their time accessing the Internet through a variety of technological devices. Research by McAfee (2014) reports that 92% of Indian teenagers report being online every day and 24% reported being online "almost constantly". Almost three-quarters of teenagers in India have access to a smartphone, allowing for ever-increasing access to the Internet.^[1] In response to the higher number of internet users, researchers have investigated how general internet use may affect the mental health and well-being of young adolescents. For example, Belanger, Akre, Berchtold, and Michaud (2011) found that both heavy Internet users and non-Internet users were at increased risk for poorer mental health and increased psychosomatic health problems.^[2] In comparison, there is not much knowledge about the potential risks to adolescents who use the Internet specifically to access social media and social networking sites.

According to Lenhart (2015), the most frequently used social networks are Facebook (41%), Instagram (20%), Snapchat (11%), Twitter (6%), Google+ (5%), Tumblr (3%), Vine (1%), and other social media sites (1%).^[3] (See Figure:1). With the adaptive and evolving nature of modern technology and tools, social media and social networking sites are constantly updating and changing. In addition, new sites are constantly being created. From the beginning of 2008 to the end of 2010, a page called Instagram fell from the most popular social network and was overshadowed by the emerging competitor Facebook. Constant shifts in popularity between sites can make it challenging for researchers to compare the effects of using social media sites from year to year or even month to month. Research by Lenhart (2015) found that 71% of teens reported using more than one form of social networking, which may also pose a

problem when comparing teens' use of social media and social networking sites.^[3] It is important to consider the terms "social media" and "social network" and the context in which they are used in this document. Originally, the difference between the two could be distinguished based on their properties and functions. However, as all of these social networking sites are updated, there is more and more overlap in the features that social media offers versus social networking sites. Social media sites originally focused on providing an outlet for broadcasts, while social networks were used as a way to communicate, share files, and connect with others.^[4]

Now, with so much overlap in functionality, both types of sites allow users to communicate and share information, as well as videos and photos, to a controlled group of viewers or followers. Users have the option to "friend" or "follow" each other, giving them access to their posts. These sites offer users the option to express consent by sharing, commenting or "liking" posts. Some sites focus on two-way communication as a way to create and maintain connections and networks by providing features such as live chat, instant messaging, and the ability to tag specific people in comments or posts. For the purpose of this work, we have included both terms to avoid excluding studies that may differ in their definition of social media and social networking sites.

1.2 Adolescents

According to the Canadian Pediatric Society (2003), adolescents as young adults aged 10-19 yrs. although the age range is often loosely defined. Adolescence is an important time when young people are particularly susceptible to the presence and opinion of their peers, parents and friends. The research found that the presence of peers, parents and friends was associated with increased physical activity and therefore higher levels of well-being in adolescents. The presence of friends can also increase risky behavior.^[5]

1.3 Mental Health and Wellbeing

The terms "mental health" and "well-being" are terms whose definitions may vary from study to study. The lack of stable functioning of these constructs can make it difficult to measure both areas of life. Although the studies included in this systematic review may further differ in the definition and measurement of these constructs, the definitions that this article will use when referring to them are as follows. I might define "well-being" as a measure of how well someone is doing, or doing better than usual, compared to the average of the group. There are many dimensions and domains of well-being, including social, academic, emotional, physical and mental well-being.

A measure of a person's well-being may include their popularity, their academic success, how physically active they are, etc. Mental health, on the other hand, is a measure of the poor emotional and psychological characteristics that a person expresses compared to the group average.

2. Aims & Objectives:

To systematically review empirical studies conducted over the past 10 years on this topic in order to reach a consensus regarding the impact of e-media and social networking use on adolescents.

To identify any variables or predispositions that may moderate these effects.

3. Methods:

This paper reviews the existing evidence examining the effects of social media and social networking site use on adolescent mental health and well-being. Due to the presence of multiple research questions, a statistical meta-analysis was not possible; therefore a systematic review approach was used. A systematic review acts as an unbiased procedure to find relevant studies that investigate similar research questions. This systematic review was conducted in accordance with the guidelines provided on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses website (Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D. G., & The PRISMA Group, 2009). Searches were conducted through the following databases: (1) PubMed and (2) PsycINFO. PubMed is a database of life sciences and biomedicine, while PsycINFO, a database of the American Psychological Association, has both practical literature and academic research in psychology. The focus on mental health and well-being makes these two databases the most appropriate to use. The search process included only these two databases as they provided the most appropriate coverage of the relevant literature. A first search was performed on PubMed using the terms (Social Networking Use) OR (Social Media) OR (Social Networking Sites) AND (Mental Health) OR (Well-Being). Inclusion restrictions were: free full text, studies conducted in the last 10 years, humans and adolescents (13-18 years). The result was 443 results. Based on the titles, a large proportion of the results focused on social media and social networking sites as intervention and treatment tools and therefore classified them as irrelevant.

In order to narrow the search to more relevant studies, search terms were modified to ('Social Media' OR 'Social Networking Sites') AND ('Mental Health' OR 'Wellbeing') NOT ('Intervention') with restrictions set to English, Adolescents

(13-18 years old), person and date of publication in the last 10 years (2008-2018). The same search terms were then used in a PsycINFO search, but with restrictions on humans, adolescents (aged 13–17 years), and empirical study methodology. The updated search narrowed the results to 37 studies from PubMed and 32 studies from PsycINFO. All 69 studies were then entered into an Excel spreadsheet and duplicates were removed and flagged in 66 studies (See Figure: 2). The next step was to read all 66 abstracts and remove additional studies based on relevance. Any study that was either a systematic review or a meta-analysis was immediately removed. Studies were included if they 1) measured the effects of social media use and social networking sites, and 2) looked at moderators that may influence how adolescent mental health and well-being were affected by social media use. All studies with irrelevant abstracts were removed, resulting in 26 remaining studies. These 26 studies were thoroughly read and a further 13 studies were removed based on non-relevance. An additional study was excluded due to the impossibility of accessing the full text.^[6] The 13 studies were organized into a table that detailed the research question, methodology, sample size, and demographics, as well as the results and limitations of each study. Using a graph, studies were analyzed using a narrative synthesis approach and examined under the following frameworks: (1) Harmful exposure, (2) Peer support, and (3) Addiction related to social media and social networking use.

4.Results

4.1 Study Methodologies and Participant Characteristics

The methodology of the studies used in this systematic review varied between studies. The majority of studies in this systematic review (84.61%) used a type of cross-sectional methodology in the form of questionnaires, surveys and various measures. However, research conducted by Naslund et al. (2014) and Moreno et al (2016) used an alternative approach^[7]. Both studies used specific search terms to search for public posts on YouTube and Instagram and then analyzed the results for the presence of peer support, signs of social media addiction, as well as harmful thoughts. Both studies used one-shot searches. All 13 studies used were conducted within eight years from 2008 to 2018. Overall, the teenage participants ranged in age from 10 to 30 years old, as did one study where participants were up to 75 years old, but with an average age of 27.53.

However, most studies included participants within the adolescent age ranges used by these two databases (PubMed = 13-18; PsycINFO = 13-17). Participant sizes also varied substantially, from as small as the analysis of 19 YouTube videos to sample sizes reaching nearly 11,000.

The 13 studies included in this review examined different social networks and social networking sites. The most frequently investigated site was Facebook^[8]. The repeated use of this social networking site may be due to its large number of users with reports of over five hundred million users in 2010 and it has also been found to be the most popular social media and social networking site among teenagers.^[9]

4.2 Social Media and Social Networking Site Usage and Exposure to Potentially Harmful Information and Ideations

A concern with teens using social media and social networking sites is the potential for them to encounter or be exposed to harmful information and negative experiences. Research by Dunlop et al. (2011) found that Facebook use had the potential to expose adolescents to information about suicide that could potentially lead to the user's own suicidal ideation. Although social media was reported to be where 25% of suicidal exposures occurred, no change was found in adolescent suicidal ideation. Therefore, this research shows that although using Facebook as a social networking site may increase adolescents' exposure to information about suicide, its use alone does not increase adolescent suicide or suicidal ideation compared to receiving similar information from family and friends.

Ybarra and Mitchell's (2008) research also addressed the issue of how using social networking sites can lead to exposure to potentially harmful information or interactions. Specifically, they examined risky social networking sites presented to adolescents with regard to encounters with unwanted sexual harassment and sexual harassment through site features such as chat rooms, instant messaging, and online journals. Their findings indicate that 4% of all youth reported being the target of unwanted sexual requests specifically through social networking sites, and 9% of all youth reported being the target of sexual harassment through these sites.^[10] Although only a small percentage of adolescent users reported these adverse experiences, the results show that the use of social media and social networking sites can expose young users to adverse negative experiences that they might not otherwise experience. A third study by Moreno et al. (2016) focused on how social

media use can expose adolescents to harmful thoughts through the use of Instagram hashtags(#). Ten ambiguous non-suicidal self-harm hashtags(#) were identified and examined. As many of the identified non-suicidal self-harm terms are ambiguous, such as #cat, the overlap means that adolescent viewers may encounter these images by accident. These authors suggested that exposure to suicidal self-injury (NSSI) from peers may lead to an increase in adolescent engagement in these behaviors as well as a normalization of these actions. The results found that the type of relationship an adolescent with NSSI had had influenced how they responded to these hashtags. Adolescents involved in NSSI may feel a sense of connectedness or engage in NSSI behaviors in response to these hashtags. For adolescents curious about NSSI, these hashtags can provide instructions on how to self-injure or normalize these actions as available emotional outlets. It also found that only one-third of hashtags triggered a Content Advisory. Therefore, it can be concluded that Instagram does not have enough warnings when it comes to protecting teenagers from exposure to self-harming content.

4.3 Social Media and Social Networking Site Usage and Peer Support

Another question is whether social networking sites can provide adolescents with peer support and a sense of connectedness and thus be beneficial to their well-being. Peer support has been shown to be beneficial for young adults in many aspects of mental well-being, leading to the question of whether peer support can be obtained through social networking sites in real life. For example, through Facebook, adolescents have access to a source of social support that is linked to higher levels of well-being^[11].

Best et al. (2015) found that the greater number of friends an adolescent male had online was associated with higher well-being scores, although it was also associated with negative factors such as greater exposure to strangers and embarrassing comments and posts. A higher number of friends online creates a perception of social support, social status, and a sense of belonging.^[12] The result of these perceptions is an overall positive feeling of well-being. When faced with negative experiences such as cyber bullying, adolescents with a more supportive social network were less likely to view these experiences as harmful. Therefore, although the number of online friends is in some cases related to a higher sense of mutual support and well-being, it was

found that the quality over the quantity of relationships is what has a greater impact on the well-being of adolescent males.

4.4 Social Media and Social Networking Site Addiction and Prolonged Periods of Use

Several studies used in this systematic review focused on the relationship between adolescent mental health and well-being and addiction to social media and social networking sites. Research has shown that pre-existing anxiety, insomnia and depression were predictors of adolescent Facebook addiction. This study also found that those who used Facebook often reported higher levels of Facebook addiction. Similarly, Blanchino et al. (2015) also found that in addition to pre-existing depression, adolescent males who spent large amounts of time online would predictably develop Facebook addiction.^[13]

Long-term use of Facebook can also lead to the development of depressive symptoms due to low self-esteem. This low self-esteem can arise from constantly watching the successes and achievements of their peers, which can cause them to reflect negatively on their own lives in comparison.^[14]

Excessive Facebook use may also pose an increased risk of potentially harmful effects on adolescent well-being by interfering with academic performance, sleep hours, and productivity, which may lead to depression^[8].

The results also showed that time spent on social media increased based on higher levels of depression. Therefore, it has been found that there is a relationship between depression and time spent using social networking sites, but without longitudinal and interventional research, the directionality of this correlation is unclear.

Another way that excessive use of social media and social networking sites can negatively affect teens is through physical health. Computer use is associated with lower physical health, such as back pain and headaches,^[15] the severity of which may be minimized by moderate use in adolescents who access social networks through computers.^[16] confirmed this by finding a positive correlation between greater use of social networks and somatic complaints, specifically back pain. The use of social networking sites can lead to negative effects on the well-being of adolescents, depending on the amount of time a person spends on these sites on a daily basis.

5. Discussion:

This systematic review sought to organize and summarize studies conducted over the past 10 years to help determine the impact of social media and social networking site use on adolescent mental health and well-being. The studies used in this systematic review showed results supporting the positive aspects of social media and networking use, as well as the harmful aspects. It has been found that not all teenagers react to the use of social networks in the same way. There are characteristics that influence what effects an adolescent may experience when using social media and social networking sites.

5.1 Moderators of Beneficial Effects of Social Media and Social Networking Sites

By examining 13 studies, We found that the reported benefits of using social media and social networking sites include an increased sense of belonging, connectedness, as well as a way to gain peer support and maintain relationships. Adolescents who use social media as a method of coping with their mental disorders have been found to often experience peer support that minimizes their sense of isolation and the challenges of everyday life^[16]. This effect has been observed in individuals with schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder and bipolar disorder^[7]. It is important to consider that social media and social networking can provide a false or exaggerated sense of social support that may not be present off-screen. A similar result has been observed in suicidal adolescents^[17] as well as those struggling with insomnia, depression and anxiety^[8]. It can be concluded that the use of social media and social networking sites can provide social support and thus benefit the mental health and well-being of adolescents, especially those who struggle with mental health problems and insomnia.

5.2 Moderators of Negative Effects of Social Media and Social Networking Site Usage

Several harmful effects of using social media and social networking sites have also been identified. One of the negative effects of using these sites is the possibility of experiencing unwanted sexual harassment. The probability of this effect is higher in female users. Older youth are also more likely to be the target of online harassment due to the higher number of older youth owning social media and social media accounts^[10]. Use of these sites may also lead to harmful content such as images and information about self-harm.

To minimize these negative effects, users of social media and social networking sites should limit their daily usage time to two hours and also start using them at an older age. Social sites must be aware of these harmful effects and find ways to combat exposure to harmful content and online harassment.

5.3 Limitations

These findings have some significant limitations that may have affected the results. Due to the limited amount of research on this topic, this review had a relatively small study scope of only 13 relevant studies. It is possible that with a larger study size, a more concrete consensus on potential effects could have been reached. There was also a significant difference between the years in which these studies were conducted. Social media and social networking sites have changed tremendously in 10 years, causing a social networking site in 2008 to have many different features than a site in 2018. These added features and new sites may have a different effect on teens than past features.

6. Conclusion :

This review revealed inconsistent evidence showing both the benefits and harms of using electronic media such as; mobile with internet and social networking sites like; Facebook, Instagram and Twitter etc.

The younger generation of today is emerging as an active social media user who has an affinity for mental health issues. A proper awareness movement can be organized to understand the effects of social media use on mental health in the younger generation.

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